

TIME-FREQUENCY ANALYSIS OF MODEL BASED PULSE SCATTERING FROM A FLUID-ELASTIC INTERFACE WITH PERIODIC ROUGHNESS

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Abstract-A null field T-matrix formalism [1] is used to calculate time series produced by scattering a linear frequency modulated plane wave pulse from a doubly infinite fluid-elastic interface with sinusoidal and triangular roughness. The time series are analyzed using short time Fourier and Wigner-Ville transforms and an adaptive waveform transform based on local cosine waveforms [2]. It is shown that the time-frequency (T-F) analysis provided by the adaptive waveform transform may be used to distinguish between the scatter from surfaces of different roughness types and, for this purpose, is superior to the T-F analysis provided by both the short time Fourier and Wigner-Ville transforms.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a great deal of interest in analytical techniques that can analyze the acoustic scatter from a rough surface and determine the type of surface roughness. The utility of such techniques ranges from non-destructive analysis of materials to determine, for example, the existence of cracks, to non-invasive analysis of the surface roughness of pathological tissue to determine the type of pathology. In general, it is advantageous to insonify the surface with a broad band pulse and analyze the scatter as a function of time. It is then quite natural to consider time-frequency (T-F) analysis of the scattered pulse. Time-frequency analysis is not new and a wide variety of techniques have been developed and widely used to analyze time series [3]. In this paper, a null field T-matrix model for plane wave scattering from a doubly infinite fluid-solid interface with periodic roughness and elastic boundary conditions [1] is used to calculate scattering of a linear frequency modulated (LFM) plane wave pulse in the frequency domain. Then an inverse Fourier transform is used to calculate the time series of the scattered pressure pulse in the fluid. The time series are analyzed using short time Fourier and Wigner-Ville transforms and an adaptive waveform transform based on a local cosine transform. Then the ability of T-F analysis to distinguish between types of surface roughness is investigated.

It is assumed that a pulse is propagating in an infinite, homogeneous, and isotropic fluid half space and is incident on and is scattered from the doubly infinite surface of a homogeneous and isotropic elastic half space on which there is periodic roughness. The roughness is periodic along the x and y axes and has an amplitude $z = \xi(x,y)$ where $\xi(x,y)$ is the roughness profile function. Along the x -axis (y -axis) it

has a maximum amplitude a_x (a_y), period Λ_x (Λ_y), and wave number $K_x = 2\pi/\Lambda_x$ ($K_y = 2\pi/\Lambda_y$). In this paper, sinusoidal and triangular roughness profile functions are considered. The Lamé parameters and mass density are, respectively, $\lambda^{(1)}$ and $\rho^{(1)}$ for the fluid and $\lambda^{(2)}$, $\mu^{(2)}$, and $\rho^{(2)}$ for the solid. For a frequency ω , the phase speed and wave number are, respectively, $c_p^{(1)} = \sqrt{\lambda^{(1)}/\rho^{(1)}}$ and $k_p^{(1)} = \omega/c_p^{(1)}$ in the fluid, and in the solid they are $c_s^{(2)} = \sqrt{\mu^{(2)}/\rho^{(2)}}$ and $k_s^{(2)} = \omega/c_s^{(2)}$ and $k_p^{(2)} = \omega/c_p^{(2)}$ for s-waves and $k_p^{(2)} =$

$\sqrt{(\lambda^{(2)} + 2\mu^{(2)})/\rho^{(2)}}$ and $k_p^{(2)} = \omega/c_p^{(2)}$ for p-waves. The unknown fields are the scattered pressure field in the fluid

$p^{(s)}(\vec{r}, t)$, the scattered displacement field in the solid

$\vec{u}^{(s)}(\vec{r}, t)$, the surface pressure field $p_+(\vec{r}, t)$, and the surface

displacement field $\vec{u}_-(\vec{r}, t)$. The subscripts + and - are used, respectively, to denote that a surface field is evaluated in the limit in which r' approaches the surface from the volume above and below the surface. At the fluid-elastic interface, the surface fields must satisfy the following boundary conditions; (1) the normal component of the displacement and traction are continuous and (2) the tangential component of the traction vanishes.

It is assumed that all fields can be represented by a Fourier integral in the following manner;

$$\phi(\vec{r}, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\omega \phi(\vec{r}, \omega) e^{-i\omega t} \quad (1a)$$

with

$$\phi(\vec{r}, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt \phi(\vec{r}, t) e^{i\omega t} \quad (1b)$$

and where $\phi(\vec{r}, t)$ is the time domain representation of any of the unknown scattered or surface fields and $\phi(\vec{r}, \omega)$ is the corresponding frequency domain representation.

It is assumed that the incident pulse is of the form $p^{(i)}(\vec{r}, t) = p^{(i)}(\vec{r}) p^{(i)}(t)$ and that in the frequency domain it is a plane wave pulse with

$$p^{(i)}(\vec{r}, \omega) = p^{(i)}(\omega) \exp(\vec{k}_p^{(i)} \cdot \vec{r}) \quad (2)$$

where $p^{(i)}(\omega)$ is the Fourier transform of $p^{(i)}(t)$. In this paper $p^{(i)}(t)$ is an LFM pulse given by

$$p^{(i)}(t) = \begin{cases} e^{-i[(\omega_0+at)t]} & (0 \leq t \leq \tau) \\ 0 & (t > \tau) \\ 0 & (t < 0) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The parameter τ is the pulse length, the product $a\tau$ determines the bandwidth, and for $a > (<) 0$, the parameter ω_0 determines the lowest (highest) frequency in the pulse.

II. A T-MATRIX FOR PULSE SCATTERING FROM A FLUID-SOLID INTERFACE WITH PERIODIC SURFACE ROUGHNESS

A. Helmholtz-Kirchhoff representations for scattered and surface fields

Since the T-matrix formalism for pulse scattering is an extension of that developed previously for plane wave scattering [1], it is described briefly. In the frequency domain, the Helmholtz-Kirchhoff (HK) representation of the displacement field produced by the scatter of an acoustic pulse in the fluid from a fluid-solid interface with periodic roughness and the null field equation that follows from the extended boundary condition are given by [1]

$$-\int_0^{\Lambda_x} dx' \int_0^{\Lambda_y} dy' [p_+(\vec{r}', \omega) \vec{n}(\vec{r}') \cdot \vec{G}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \vec{k}_p^{(2)}, \vec{k}_s^{(2)}) + \vec{u}_-(\vec{r}, \omega) \cdot [\vec{n}(\vec{r}') \cdot \vec{\Sigma}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \vec{k}_p^{(2)}, \vec{k}_s^{(2)})]] = \begin{cases} \vec{u}^{(s)}(\vec{r}, \omega) & (z < -h) \\ 0 & (z > h) \end{cases} \quad (4a)$$

with $h = \max(a_x, a_y)$. To obtain (4a) and (4b), the Floquet theorem and the boundary conditions were used. The vectors \vec{r} and \vec{r}' are, respectively, radius vectors to a field point and to a point on the surface. The vector $\hat{n}(\vec{r}')$ is the unit vector normal to the surface directed in the positive z-direction. The quantities $p_+(\vec{r}', \omega)$ and $\vec{u}_-(\vec{r}, \omega)$ are the Fourier transforms of the surface fields and $\vec{u}^{(s)}(\vec{r}, \omega)$ is the Fourier transform of the scattered displacement field. The tensors $\vec{\Sigma}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \vec{k}_p^{(2)}, \vec{k}_s^{(2)})$ and $\vec{G}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \vec{k}_p^{(2)}, \vec{k}_s^{(2)})$ are, respectively, the free space stress and displacement Green tensors for a double periodic array of unit impulse body forces. The vectors $\vec{k}_p^{(2)}$ and $\vec{k}_s^{(2)}$ are, respectively, the wave vectors for p and s waves with $k_{px}^{(2)} = k_{sx}^{(2)} = k_{px}^{(1)}$, $k_{py}^{(2)} =$

$k_{sy}^{(2)} = k_{py}^{(1)}$, $k_{pz}^{(2)} = \sqrt{k_p^{(2)2} - k_{px}^{(2)2} - k_{py}^{(2)2}}$, and $k_{sz}^{(2)} = \sqrt{k_s^{(2)2} - k_{sx}^{(2)2} - k_{sy}^{(2)2}}$. The quantities $k_{px}^{(1)}$ and $k_{py}^{(1)}$ are, respectively, the x and y-components of the p-wave vector

in the fluid. The branch cut used to evaluate the z-component of these wave vectors and all subsequent wave vectors is chosen to satisfy the radiation boundary condition. The equality of the horizontal components of the wave vectors is necessary to enforce the boundary conditions.

In the frequency domain, the HK representation of the scattered pressure field in a fluid and the null field equation are given by

$$\int_0^{\Lambda_x} dx' \int_0^{\Lambda_y} dy' [p_+(\vec{r}', \omega) \vec{n}(\vec{r}') \cdot \vec{\nabla}' g(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \vec{k}_p^{(1)}) - \lambda^{(1)} k_p^{(1)2} g(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \vec{k}_p^{(1)}) \vec{n}(\vec{r}') \cdot \vec{u}_-(\vec{r}, \omega)] = \begin{cases} p^{(s)}(\vec{r}, \omega) & (z > h) \\ -p^{(i)}(\vec{r}, \omega) & (z < -h) \end{cases} \quad (5a)$$

where $p^{(i)}(\vec{r}, \omega)$ is the Fourier transform of the scattered pressure field and $g(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \vec{k}_p^{(1)})$ is the scalar Green function for a double periodic array of impulse sources.

B. Field Representations

To represent the various scalar and tensor fields, scalar and vector rectangular basis functions are constructed from Floquet plane waves. To simplify notation, the superscripts that refer to the fluid and the solid are temporarily omitted. The m-th order Floquet plane wave is given by

$$\chi(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_m^{(\pm)}) = \exp(\vec{k}_m^{(\pm)} \cdot \vec{r}) \quad (6)$$

with $k_{xm_x} = k_x + m_x K_x$, $k_{ym_y} = k_y + m_y K_y$, and $k_{zm} =$

$\sqrt{k^2 - k_{xm_x}^2 - k_{ym_y}^2}$. To simplify notation the index \vec{m} is used to denote the ordered pair (m_x, m_y) where m_x and m_y are integers that determine the mode. Rectangular vector basis functions are defined in the following manner:

$$\hat{\Psi}_1(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{sm}^{(\pm)}) = (k_s k_{tm}^{-1})^{-1} \vec{\nabla}_x \vec{\nabla}_x \chi(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{sm}^{(\pm)}) \quad (7a)$$

$$\hat{\Psi}_2(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{sm}^{(\pm)}) = k_{tm}^{-1} \vec{\nabla}_x \chi(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{sm}^{(\pm)}) \quad (7b)$$

and

$$\hat{\Psi}_3(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{pm}^{(\pm)}) = k_p^{-1} \vec{\nabla} \chi(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{pm}^{(\pm)}) \quad (7c)$$

The quantity k_{tm} is the magnitude of the transverse wave

vector $\vec{k}_{tm} = \vec{k}_{tm} \cdot \hat{z}$. It is important to note that the rectangular basis functions for propagating s-waves (p-waves) that have the same sign for the z-component of the wave vector are orthonormal.

The scalar and vector basis functions are used to represent the surface and scattered field in the following manner:

$$\vec{u}_-(\vec{r}, \omega) = \sum_{\vec{n}=-\infty}^{\infty} u_{\kappa\vec{n}}^-(\omega) \hat{\Psi}_{\kappa}(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{\kappa\vec{n}}^{(2+)}) \quad (8a)$$

$$\vec{u}_+^{(s)}(\vec{r}, \omega) = \sum_{\vec{m}=-\infty}^{\infty} u_{\kappa\vec{m}}^{(s)}(\omega) \hat{\Psi}_{\kappa}(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{\kappa\vec{m}}^{(2-)}), \quad (8b)$$

$$p_+(\vec{r}, \omega) = \lambda^{(1)} k_p^{(1)} \sum_{\vec{n}=-\infty}^{\infty} p_n^-(\omega) \chi(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{\vec{n}}^{(1+)}) \quad (8c)$$

and

$$p^{(s)}(\vec{r}, \omega) = \lambda^{(1)} k_p^{(1)} \sum_{\vec{m}=-\infty}^{\infty} p_m^{(s)}(\omega) \chi(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{\vec{m}}^{(1+)}) \quad (8d)$$

In (8a)-(8d), $\vec{r}'_{\perp} = x'\hat{x}' + y'\hat{y}'$, $\vec{k}_{\kappa\vec{n}}^{(2\pm)} = \vec{k}_{\vec{s}\vec{m}}^{(2\pm)} (\delta_{\kappa,1} + \delta_{\kappa,2}) + \vec{k}_{\vec{p}\vec{m}}^{(2\pm)} \delta_{\kappa,3}$, and the summation convention is used to indicate

a sum over repeated indices κ and κ' . The quantities $u_{\kappa\vec{n}}^-(\omega)$ [$u_{\kappa\vec{m}}^{(s)}(\omega)$] and $p_n^-(\omega)$ [$p_m^{(s)}(\omega)$] are the unknown spectral amplitudes of the surface [scattered] fields

Expressions for the scalar Green function, the Green displacement dyadic and stress triadic in terms of the appropriate scalar and rectangular vector basis functions are given by

$$g(\vec{r}', \vec{r}; k_p^{(1)}) = \frac{i}{2\Lambda_x \Lambda_y} \sum_{\vec{m}=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k_{\vec{p}\vec{m}}^{(1)}} \chi(\vec{r}-\vec{r}'; \vec{k}_{\vec{p}\vec{m}}^{(1\pm)}) \quad (z > z') \quad (9)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{G}(\vec{r}', \vec{r}; \vec{k}_p^{(2)}, \vec{k}_s^{(2)}) &= \frac{i}{2\rho^{(2)} \omega^2 \Lambda_x \Lambda_y} \sum_{\vec{m}=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{k_{\vec{s}\vec{m}}^{(2)}}{k_{\vec{p}\vec{m}}^{(2)}} \\ &\hat{\Psi}_{\kappa}(\vec{r}'; \vec{k}_{\kappa\vec{m}}^{(2\pm)}) \hat{\Psi}_{\kappa'}(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{\kappa\vec{m}}^{(2\pm)}) \quad (z > z') \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{\Sigma}(\vec{r}', \vec{r}; \vec{k}_p^{(2)}, \vec{k}_s^{(2)}) &= \frac{i}{2\rho^{(2)} \omega^2 \Lambda_x \Lambda_y} \sum_{\vec{m}=-\infty}^{\infty} \\ &\left\{ \frac{\mu_{\vec{s}\vec{m}}^{(2)} k_{\vec{s}\vec{m}}^{(2)2}}{k_{\vec{p}\vec{m}}^{(2)}} [\vec{\nabla}' \hat{\Psi}_{\kappa}(\vec{r}'; \vec{k}_{\kappa\vec{m}}^{(2\pm)}) \hat{\Psi}_{\kappa'}(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{\kappa\vec{m}}^{(2\pm)}) + \right. \\ &\left. \hat{\Psi}_{\kappa}(\vec{r}'; \vec{k}_{\kappa\vec{m}}^{(2\pm)}) \vec{\nabla}' \hat{\Psi}_{\kappa'}(\vec{r}; \vec{k}_{\kappa\vec{m}}^{(2\pm)}) \right\} \quad (z > z'). \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

C. A T-matrix for scattering from a fluid-solid interface with double periodic surface roughness.

The T-matrix relates the spectral amplitudes of the scattered fields to the spectral amplitudes of the incident field. To obtain equations for the spectral amplitudes of the scattered and surface fields, the representations of the various scalar and tensor fields are used in the HK equations for the scattered fields and in the null field equations. Then the orthogonal properties of the basis functions are used to project the results. These calculations produce two doubly infinite systems of coupled matrix equations. The system of equations obtained from the scattered field equations can be used to express the scattered field spectral amplitudes in terms of the surface field spectral amplitudes. Then the system of equations obtained from the null field equations can be solved to express the surface field spectral amplitudes in terms of the spectrum of the incident field. The result of these calculations is given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_{1\vec{m}}^{(s)}(\omega) \\ u_{2\vec{m}}^{(s)}(\omega) \\ u_{3\vec{m}}^{(s)}(\omega) \\ p_{\vec{m}}^{(s)}(\omega) \end{pmatrix} = T_{\vec{m}\vec{n}}^{(s)}(\omega) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -p_{\vec{n}}^{(i)}(\omega) \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where the T-matrix is given by

$$T_{\vec{m}\vec{n}}^{(s)}(\omega) = Q_{\vec{m}\vec{n}}^{\leftrightarrow(-)}(\omega) [Q_{\vec{m}\vec{n}}^{\leftrightarrow(+)}(\omega)]^{-1} \quad (13)$$

and the matrices $Q_{\vec{m}\vec{n}}^{\leftrightarrow(-)}(\omega)$ and $Q_{\vec{m}\vec{n}}^{\leftrightarrow(+)}(\omega)$ are infinite coefficient matrices from the HK and null field equations, respectively, and are given in [1]

The final expression for the scattered pressure field is given by

$$p^{(s1)}(\vec{r}, t) = -\lambda^{(1)} k_p^{(1)} \sum_{\vec{m}=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{\vec{n}=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\omega T_{\vec{m}\vec{n}}^{(s)}(\omega) p_{\vec{n}}^{(i)}(\omega) e^{i(\vec{k}_{\vec{m}}^{(1+)} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega t)} \quad (14)$$

IV. TIME-FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

A. The time-frequency plane

In this paper, time-frequency (T-F) representations of $p^{(s1)}(\vec{r}, t)$ are constructed using a short time Fourier transform (STFT), Wigner-Ville discrete time transform (WVDT), and an adaptive waveform transform (AWT) based on a local cosine transform (LCT). In each case, the T-F representation is constructed by segmenting or windowing the signal in time and then calculating the frequency spectrum. However, the resolution of the signal in the T-F plane is limited by the uncertainty principle. The uncertainty principle is expressed by the fact that the time-

bandwidth product of a finite pulse is a constant i.e., $\Delta t \Delta f \geq 1$. In the T-F plane, the time-bandwidth product describes a cell, called a Heisenberg cell. Heisenberg cells are disjoint, and provide a tiling of the entire T-F plane. The area and aspect ratio of the cells depend on the transform used to represent the signal. The T-F representation of a signal is displayed graphically in a T-F plane in which the Heisenberg cells are shaded in proportion to the T-F spectral amplitude. This method of displaying the T-F representation of a signal is somewhat unconventional, but is consistent with the uncertainty principle. In addition, when the AWT is used to calculate the T-F representation of a signal, this type of representation can be used to reconstruct the signal from a portion of its T-F spectrum.

The use of STFT and WVD for constructing T-F representations of a signal are standard techniques and are reviewed in [3]. The AWT is used to provide an optimal representation and is described in [2]. However, since the AWT is less well known, it is described briefly.

B. Adaptive waveform transform

The adaptive waveform transform used in this paper was introduced in [2] and uses an adaptive windowed local cosine transform. The AWT is used to construct a near optimal segmentation which is equivalent to a near-optimal localization in time and frequency. An optimal segmentation minimizes the number of large amplitude Heisenberg cells and the shaded area in the graphical display of the T-F representation. To obtain an optimal segmentation in time, the original signal is segmented following a dyadic tree structure. The optimal distribution of windows is obtained by comparing the T-F representation of the signal using two adjacent intervals with that produced by their union. The optimal window is the one that for a fixed number of largest coefficients maximizes energy or minimizes entropy. An optimal segmentation consists of a distribution of windows obtained from different levels of the dyadic tree and its graphical display is characterized by Heisenberg cells with different aspect ratios. A best level representation is obtained by using an optimal uniform segmentation and its graphical display is characterized by Heisenberg cells with a constant aspect ratio.

The novel feature of the AWT transform introduced in [2] is the use of the bell shaped window $w_j(t)$ introduced by Coifman and Meyer [4]. On the interval $I_j = [a_j, a_{j+1}]$ with length l_j , $w_j(t)$ satisfies the following conditions:

$$0 \leq w_j(t) \leq 1, \quad (15a)$$

$$w_j(t) = 1 \quad t \in [a_j + \epsilon_j, a_{j+1} - \epsilon_{j+1}], \quad (15b)$$

$$0 \quad t \notin [a_j - \epsilon_j, a_{j+1} + \epsilon_{j+1}],$$

$$w_j(t) = w_{j-1}(2a_{j+1} - t), \quad (15c)$$

and

$$w_j^2(t) + w_{j-1}^2(t) = 1 \quad |t - a_j| \leq \epsilon_j. \quad (15d)$$

The windows that satisfy the conditions in (15) extend beyond the interval I_j and provide a smooth and symmetrical overlap with adjacent windows. The basis functions introduced in [4] are given by

$$u_{j,k}(t) = \sqrt{2/l_j} w_j(t) \cos[\pi(k+1/2)(t-a_j)/l_j]. \quad (16)$$

The basis functions $u_{j,k}(t)$ are orthonormal not only within the interval I_j , but throughout the T-F plane. It can be shown that if a function $f(t) \in L^2(\mathbb{R})$, then it can be represented in the following manner:

$$f(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} c_{j,k} u_{j,k}(t) \quad (17a)$$

with

$$c_{j,k} = \frac{\int_{a_j - \epsilon_j}^{a_{j+1} + \epsilon_{j+1}} dt f_j(t) u_{j,k}(t)}{\int_{a_j}^{a_{j+1}} dt s_j(t) \sqrt{2/l_j} \cos[\pi(k+1/2)(t-a_j)/l_j]} \quad (17b)$$

and

$$s_j(t) = f(t) w_j(t) - f(2a_j - t) + f(2a_{j+1} - t) w_j(2a_{j+1} - t). \quad (17c)$$

The effect of the window $w_j(t)$ is evident in (17) where it is shown that the energy in the overlap region is folded back into the interval I_j and the function $s_j(t)$ is projected out from $f(t)$ and onto the basis functions. Using the representation given in (17a), a signal can be represented by an optimal T-F spectrum and the spectrum can be used to reconstruct the signal. In addition, there is no energy leakage between adjacent Heisenberg boxes and the uncertainty principle is obeyed.

V. NUMERICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Numerical procedures and algorithms used to calculate the frequency domain T-matrix are described in [1]. To calculate the spectrum of the incident pulse, the fast Fourier transform (FFT) subroutine FFTCF [5] was used. The number of time samples was $N = 2^n$ where n is an integer determined by dividing the width of the time window of the FFT by the sample frequency chosen so that the Nyquist frequency equals the highest frequency in the pulse. To calculate the time series of the scattered pulse, the T-matrix was calculated at 4096 frequencies and then a four point Lagrange interpolation routine was used to provide

the remaining $N-4096$ frequency samples. The FFT subroutine FFTCB was used to calculate the inverse Fourier integral.

To be able to determine the effects on scattering of various parameters, a basis set of parameters was chosen and is given by $\theta^{(i)} = \phi^{(i)} = 45^\circ$, $a_x = a_y = 0.05$ m, and $\Lambda_x = \Lambda_y = 2$ m, $\rho^{(1)} = 1000$ kg/m³, $c_p^{(1)} = 1493$ m/s, $c_p^{(2)} = 2400$ m/s, $c_s^{(2)} = 900$ m/s, $\rho^{(2)} = 2000$ kg/m³. The pulse parameters are, $\tau = 0.2$ s, $\omega_0 = 2$ kHz, and $a = 30$ kHz, so that the bandwidth is 6 kHz.

VI. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

To illustrate the advantage of the AWT, the WVDT transform was used to calculate the T-F representation of the backscatter from a fluid-elastic interface with sinusoidal roughness. The results of this calculation are shown in Fig. 1. This figure clearly shows the presence of the LFM nature of the scattered pulse. However, it is also evident that the WVDT transform does not provide localization in the T-F plane and there are spurious frequencies present. Figures. 2a and 2b show, respectively, best level basis T-F representations obtained from an AWT for back scattering from sinusoidal and triangular surface roughness. In both figures, the LFM nature of the scatter is evident. However, it is also evident that in contrast to the WVDT transform, the AWT provides representations that are localized in the T-F plane. By way of contrast, the optimal basis T-F representation for back scattering from sinusoidal surface roughness is shown in Fig 3. The optimal basis is characterized by Heisenberg cells whose aspect ratio varies and somewhat improved localization in the T-F plane. Because the AWT is a linear transform and because basis functions that represent the signal within each Heisenberg cell are orthonormal, it is meaningful to subtract the T-F representation of the backscatter from the sinusoidal and triangular roughness to determine the difference spectrum. The results of this calculation are shown in Fig. 4. It is evident that the difference between the scatter from these two types of surface roughness is greatest at high frequencies. Although this result is not new, the fact this result can be obtained by subtracting the AWT T-F representations of the two time series is one of the novel and significant results of this work. In addition, the difference T-F spectrum shown in Fig. 4 can be used in its entirety or in part to reconstruct the difference signal. Calculations have shown that approximately 95% of the energy of the original signal is contained in a signal constructed from approximately the 75 highest amplitude AWT T-F spectral coefficients. In addition, the data compression obtained by the AWT allows the results shown in these figures to be used to train and test pattern recognition algorithms (e.g., neural nets). Although this

Fig. 1. Wigner-Ville transform T-F representation of the backscatter of an LFM pulse from a fluid-elastic interface with sinusoidal roughness.

paper has been concerned with differentiating between the scatter from two types of surface roughness, it appears that the same techniques can be used to differentiate between the scatter from other types of scatterers (e.g., an elastic shell and a rough surface).

It has been shown that when T-F representations are used to differentiate between the scatter from different types of surface roughness, the AWT has many advantages over the WVDT transform and by implication many other more traditional T-F transforms. The AWT provides a T-F representation of a signal that is localized, compressed and that can be used to reconstruct a high fidelity signal from a very small number of T-F spectral coefficients. In addition, because the AWT provides a representation of a signal in terms of an orthonormal basis, the scatter from two scatterers may be compared by subtracting their AWT T-F representations.

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(2a)

(2b)

Fig. 2. Time series and adaptive local cosine transform best level basis T-F representation of the backscatter of an LFM pulse from a fluid-elastic interface with (a) sinusoidal and (b) triangular roughness.

Fig. 3. Time series and adaptive local cosine transform optimal basis T-F representation of the backscatter of an LFM pulse from a fluid-elastic interface with triangular roughness of an LFM pulse.

Fig. 4. Difference between the adaptive local cosine transform best level basis T-F representation of the backscatter of an LFM pulse from a fluid-elastic interface with sinusoidal roughness and from one with triangular roughness.